

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH USED IN SHIP STRUCTURES

Y.J. Lee Y. Shyu Y.L. Cheng
Institute of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering
National Taiwan University, Taipei, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

The impact behavior of composite sandwich panels subjected to the cylindrical and spherical impactors were investigated, respectively. Three kinds of laminated face sheets MAM, MCM, MRM (M: glass mat; C: carbon; R: glass roving; A: aramid) and two DIVINYCELL core materials with different densities ($\rho = 0.1, 0.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$) were considered. With the cylindrical impactor, the impact behavior was investigated numerically and experimentally. While with the spherical impactor, only experiments were conducted.

A drop-weight impactor tower with an adjustable impactor was used in the impact test. During the experiments with the cylindrical impactor, under the simply supported condition, the impact force and strain history were measured, and the failure patterns were inspected by visual observations. The dimensions of the specimens were $90\text{mm} \times 45\text{mm}$ and the impact energy ranged from 1 Joule to 7 Joules. One of the objectives of the impact experiment was to assess the impact resistance of these composite sandwich panels. Energy absorbed by sandwich panels after impact could be an indication to measure the impact resistance performance. In this work, energy absorption of sandwich panels was approximately equal to the loss of kinetic energy of the impactor which could be obtained through the Impulse-Momentum relationship. The experimental results indicated that the dynamic response was mainly controlled by the core material. The higher the core density was, the better the impact resistance performance was. As for the failure mode, sandwich structures with core density 0.1 tended to have shear cracks in the core material, but crush in foam core and matrix cracking in the top face sheets under the impact point were found for those with core density 0.2.

When the impactor was changed to the spherical one and the specimens were changed to $90\text{mm} \times 90\text{mm}$ square panels, the experimental result also showed that the core density still dominated the dynamic response under low impact energy. To understand the deformation configuration under simple support, several strain gages were attached on various positions of the specimens. From the strain histories, it was shown that the deformation on the top face sheets were substantially influenced by the shape of the impactor, while that on the bottom was mainly affected by the boundary condition. When the impact energy was higher than 7 Joules, the damages would occur locally in the neighborhood of the impact location. In the fracture process,

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact behavior of sandwich panels, used in ship structures, subjected to the cylindrical and spherical impactors under low impact velocity. Six kinds of sandwich panels made of various fabric-laminate and core densities are considered. Impact responses, including impact force and strain histories are measured and compared with the numerical results. Also, failure modes of specimens observed in the experiments are discussed. Finally, numerical stress analysis is conducted to find the stress distribution over the whole sandwich panel, then the estimation of fracture initiation can be obtained.

EXPERIMENTS

SPECIMENS

The face sheets of sandwich panels are made of plain-woven fabrics as specified in Table 1. Three laminated face sheets MAM, MCM, AND MRM (M: glass mat; C: carbon; R: glass roving; A: aramid) and two DIVINYCELL core materials with different densities ($\rho = 0.1, 0.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$) are taken into consideration. These sandwich panels are fabricated by IHI craft / Japan. For the reason of simplicity, sandwich panels with laminated face sheets MAM, MCM, and MRM are respectively named as such in the following article.

IMPACT TEST SYSTEM

A drop weight impactor tower with an adjustable impactor is used in the impact test. The illustration of the drop weight tower is shown in Fig.1. It consists of two vertical steel rods mounted on a heavy steel base. Attached to the vertical steel rods is an aluminum beam cross-bar with idealized frictionless sliding bearings inside. A 19 mm diameter cylindrical impactor (or a 12.7mm diameter spherical one) and a PCB200A05 force transducer are mounted on the bottom side of the cross-bar. So, the impact force history can be measured and recorded by HP5183U Data Recorder (sampling rate up to 16MHz). In addition, a simply supported fixture with span of 60mm or a fully clamped one with span of 50mm is fixed on the steel base.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CYLINDRICAL IMPACTOR

Core Density $\rho = 0.1 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Impact force histories of MAM, MCM, and MRM are shown in Fig.2. It can be seen that the impact force histories are similar to a one-half sine wave and they are nearly the same. When the impact velocity is up to about 2.0 m/s, the impact force history then has an obvious jump at 1000 μs (as shown in Fig.3). Impact cracks along 40~50 degree direction in core material are found, which locate in the region between 10mm to 20mm away from the impact point. As the impact velocity increases, the cracks will extend to the face-core interface, then induce the delamination. One of the objectives of the impact experiments is to investigate the impact resistance of sandwich panels, which can be roughly assessed by energy absorption of materials. However, it is impossible to measure them directly. But if the energy loss is assumed to be almost zero

is impossible to measure them directly. But if the energy loss is assumed to be almost zero during the impact process, then the energy absorbed by the sandwiches is approximately equal to the loss of kinetic energy of the impactor [5]. To know the kinetic energy history of the impactor during impact, it is necessary to obtain the velocity history of the impactor. Through the Impulse—Momentum relationship, the velocity history is given by

$$V(t) = V_i - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^t F dt \quad (1)$$

where V_i is the incident velocity, m is the mass of the impactor, and F is the impact force. The kinetic energy loss history of the impactor is then given by

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{2} m V_i^2 - \frac{1}{2} m V^2(t) \quad (2)$$

The impact energy vs. energy loss relationship is shown in Fig.4. There is an energy loss jump when the impact energy reaches about 3.22 Joules (critical impact energy). In the meantime, That's also when the cracks in core material are found. Therefore, the energy loss jump is due to the cracks. The critical impact energy of MAM, MCM, and MRM is shown in Table 2.

Core Density $\rho = 0.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$

When the impact energy is lower than 4 Joules, no damage is found in the specimens, and the impact force histories of MAM, MCM, and MRM are almost the same. With the increase of impact energy, the core material will crush under the impact point, while the impact force curve has no obvious jump. As the energy level is higher, apart from the increase of the crushed area, matrix crackings are found in the lowest lamina (Mat layer) of the top face sheets. The damage situations of those sandwiches are summarized briefly in Table 3.

Figure 1. Drop weight tower

Figure 2. Comparison of impact force histories

Figure 3. The impact history of sandwich panel

Figure 4. The impact energy vs. energy loss

SPHERICAL IMPACTOR

Core Density $\rho = 0.1 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Because of the geometry of the spherical impactor, it is much easier to produce local damage on specimens. Therefore, the impact energy should be low enough to keep them from producing any damages. As the preceding results are, varying the face sheets has no effect on dynamic responses of sandwich panels (as shown in Fig.5). To understand the deformation configuration under simple support condition, strain gages are attached on various positions of the surfaces. It is shown that the deformation configuration of the top surface is closely related to the impactor's geometry, but that of the bottom surface is mainly effected by the simple support condition. When the impact energy is high enough, a whitened zone due to delamination is produced right beneath the impact point. With the increase of the impact energy, there is also fiber breakage found on the lowest lamina of the top face sheets. When the face sheets are extremely damaged, the core material is crushed severely, too. The impact force histories of these 3 materials are shown in Fig.6, when the impact energy is 17 Joules,. It can be seen that the impact force history of MRM has an obvious jump which shouldn't be due to cracks in core, because none has been found in the specimens.

Core Density $\rho = 0.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Generally speaking, the dynamic behavior of sandwich panels with core density of 0.2 is qualitatively similar to those of 0.1. The impact force histories of panels with core density 0.2 have shorter time duration and higher force amplitude. At the same impact energy level, the fracture of the top face sheets and the crush of the core are less serious than those of core density 0.1.

From the foregoing results, it can be concluded that regardless of the impactors' shapes, the resistance performance is better when the core density is higher.

Figure 5. Comparison of impact force histories Figure 6. Comparison of impact force histories

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IMPACT RESPONSE ANALYSIS

The dynamic responses of the sandwich panels are also performed by the finite element software ABAQUS. Because of the line load conditions, the sandwich panels impacted by a cylindrical impactor can be modeled as a 2-D plane strain problem. A four-node, plane strain element with two degrees of freedom at each node is used. The impactor is assumed as a rigid body. The material properties of fabric-laminates and core material are referred to references[6-7].

The computed force histories of sandwich panels are compared with those obtained from the experiments. The shape of computed impact force history is nearly the same as that recorded in the experiments, but the magnitude of the computed peak force is less than that measured. As mentioned before, the core material has the dominance of the impact responses, so the understanding of the core material behavior (especially the plastic behavior) will decide if the numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental results. Unfortunately, the DIVINYCELL core material supplier didn't provide sufficient material properties which could quantitatively describe the plastic behavior of the foam core. Therefore, lack of knowledge on core material behavior should be the reason of the discrepancy between numerical solutions and experimental results. Another possible reason might attribute to neglecting the effect of strain rate.

STRESS ANALYSIS

The maximum stress criterion is used to analyze the initial fracture of sandwich structures. For simplicity, only the stress contours of MAM are demonstrated. Fig.7 shows the normalized stress contours of σ_{11} , τ_{max} , and σ_{22} of sandwich panels with core density 0.1 under the impact velocity of 1.5 m/s. The normalized stress is defined as stress divided by the strength of the material. From the results of numerical stress analysis, the in-plane normal stress distribution of face sheets is the "local bending" form. That is, the stress in the uppermost lamina of face sheets

is compressive but tensile in the lowest lamina. In Fig.7(a), it can be seen that it tends to have in-plane fracture in the uppermost lamina of face sheets due to compressive stress, but in the lowest lamina, it is due to tensile stress. However, there is no damage found in face sheets from experimental results. In Fig.7(b), the maximum normalized shear stress of 0.966 exists in the region ranging approximately from 11.2mm to 22.5mm away from the impact point. This computed region coincides fairly well with the observed region of crack damage. Similarly, the normalized out-of-plane compressive stress contour can be obtained in the same way. From the results of Fig.7(c), there should be out-of-plane compression fracture in core material. However, this fracture phenomenon hasn't been found obviously by visual observations on specimens. From the discussion, the results of numerical analysis fail to exactly predict or explain the fracture mechanism in general. The possible reasons are the errors in numerical analysis, material constants, strength, and material behavior of foam core that are not guaranteed, etc. Those should be further investigated.

Figure 7. Normalized stress contours (a) in-plane normal stress σ_{11} in top face sheets (b) Maximum shear stress τ_{max} in core material (c) out-of-plane normal stress σ_{22} in core material (MAM, core density 0.1, impact velocity 1.5m/s)

CONCLUSIONS

The dynamic responses of six kinds of sandwich panels used in ship structures under low-velocity impact are investigated experimentally and numerically. In experimental analysis, it is found that the impact behavior is mainly controlled by the core density. The higher the core density is, the better the impact resistance performance is. Generally, sandwich panels with MCM face sheets have the worst impact resistance. For failure modes, when impact energy ranges from 1 Joule to 7 Joules, sandwiches with core density of 0.1 tends to have shear crack in core material under the cylindrical impactor. Nevertheless, crush in foam core and matrix cracking in face sheets beneath the impact point are found for those with core density of 0.2. However, when the impactor is sphere-shaped and the impact energy ranges from 7 Joules to 17 Joules, fiber breakage, matrix cracking, delamination, and core crush are inspected. The damaged zone is located locally under the impact point.

In numerical analysis, the impactor is assumed as a rigid body, and a 2-D plane strain model is used. The impact responses such as impact force and strain history are compared with the experimental data. Also, the stresses within the whole sandwich are examined to estimate the initial fracture. In general, the numerical analysis performs well in prediction of dynamic response. However, there are still some problems which need to be further investigated.

Table 1. Fabric materials

Fiber	Fabric style	Fabric weight (g/m ²)
REM 300-65 Glass mat (M)	chopped	300
REM 500-M Glass roving (R)	plain woven	570
Co 6644B Carbon (C)	plain woven	300
T-900 Aramid (A)	plain woven	317

Table 2. The critical impact energy of composite sandwich (core density 0.1)

Facesheet	Critical impact energy
MAM	2.97J ~ 3.22J
MCM	2.60J ~ 2.86J
MRM	2.83J ~ 3.11J

Table 3. Fracture condition of sandwich with core density 0.2

		4 Joules	5 Joules	6 Joules	7 Joules
MAM	fiber breakage	—	—	—	—
	matrix cracking	—	×	×	×
	core crush	—	×	×	×
MCM	fiber breakage	—	—	×	×
	matrix cracking	×	×	×	×
	core crush	—	×	×	×
MRM	fiber breakage	—	—	—	—
	matrix cracking	—	—	—	×
	core crush	×	×	×	×
— no fracture occurred		×			
		× fracture occurred			

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